

Interactive Intentions of Consumers to Adopt Islamic Banking in Pakistan

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Received on: 13-10-2022

Accepted on: 21-11-2022

Abstract

One of the industries in Pakistan that is growing the fastest is Islamic banking. This study demonstrates the link between customer satisfaction and consumer behavior regarding bank choosing factors. Data was gathered for this purpose from a sample of 200 customers at various Islamic banks in Hyderabad using a standardized questionnaire with 30 questions. Data analysis has been conducted using SPSS 17. Customer satisfaction somewhat mediates the relationship between independent factors and dependent variables, according to the findings, which demonstrate positive and substantial correlations between all variables. We draw the conclusion that customers are particularly loyal to Islamic banks and that customer satisfaction is always rising.

Keywords: Islamic banking, choosing the right bank, client happiness

Introduction

The banking sector may have had a significant role in strengthening the economies of developing nations. While this is going on because it is perceived as being incompatible with Islamic beliefs and its validity has been questioned. Islamic banking, which is financial intermediation based on Islamic principles, is an alternative to regular banking. It has developed into a quickly expanding sector and is gaining popularity in both Muslim and non-Muslim nations (Abdullah & Dusuki, 2006). (Iqbal & Molyneux, 2005; Atkinson & Messy, 2011)The fact that it outlaws rib'a, gambling, and taking speculative risks is what makes it appealing from a theological and ethical perspective (Amin, Rahman, & Razak, 2014). Islamic banks do not promote any illicit enterprises since doing so would be immoral. Additionally, Islamic banks more fairly and sensibly distribute the risks and benefits of each commercial transaction. Thus, the area of Islamic banking in the financial services sector is significant and well-established. According to statistics, there are 220 Islamic Windows among the approximately 775 Islamic financial institutions functioning globally (Edbiz, 2015). Islamic assets are expected to reach \$3.8 trillion by 2022. (World Bank Group, 2018). Since it first

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started operating in Pakistan in 2002 and took on its current form, Islamic banking has coexisted with conventional banking. To encourage and advance Islamic banking, Pakistan has made tremendous efforts (Majeed & Zainab, 2017). According to the Islamic Banking Bulletin, there are currently five fully operational Islamic banks and sixteen independent Islamic banking service units operating within conventional banks in Pakistan (2017). Islamic banking products make between 12.4% and 14.5% of the market. There are 2581 operating Islamic bank branches around the country in terms of physical locations. Punjab has 47.8% of all branches.

The current study studies and investigates the customer strategy that drives consumers to choose an Islamic bank for their business. When picking a firm to invest in, people typically make very rational selections, but in the case of Muslim clients, it appears that they chose Islamic Bank mostly because of their deep-seated beliefs in Islamic trading principles. They are interested in adhering to Islamic values as well as maximising revenues and other traditional benefits. It is clearly behavioural financing if a person chooses to work with an Islamic bank largely due to their emotional and behavioural ties to their faith.

Literature

According to Urban and Pratt's (2000) analysis, managers need to be aware of the client demographics since how people perceive the quality of a service varies depending on their race, household income, gender, and level of education. This study, which was carried out in Pakistan, focused on how gender affects service quality in light of cultural considerations and socioeconomic growth. In Karachi, Azeemi et al. (2004) did study utilising questionnaires to determine whether or not customers were aware of the Shariah regulations based on the banking system. They used four sub-dimensions to check for "overall awareness," the first of which was "awareness," which measured respondents' knowledge of the Shariah-based financial system (SBFS) and their opinions on the causes of the public's lack of awareness in this area. The second sub-dimension was "differentiation," which assessed respondents' understanding of the differences between Islamic and conventional products. The third one deals with "obstacles" that are impeding the development of a financial system based on Shariah, and the final one, "acceptance," demonstrates steps that may improve the acceptability of financial services. The result demonstrates that there is a low level of societal understanding of the Shariah-based financial system. The survey offers descriptive statistics, which are valuable since they shed light on how Pakistanis are seen. According to Naeem et al. (2009)'s investigation, the central bank of Pakistan established a policy that requires the banking sector in that country to adhere to a set of standards, whether it be conventional or Islamic. However, how these standards are applied is the main concern of those who make banking policy. Additionally, they came to the conclusion that a key factor in the success of the expanding banking industry is the calibre of the people working with consumers. Additionally, they came to the conclusion that good customer service results in profit, which is the primary objective of all enterprises. Religion, according to Rehman A. and M.S. Shabbir (2010), has a significant influence in influencing people's ideas, attitudes, and knowledge as well as their decisions and actions since it educates them about what is permissible and forbidden. In contrast to conventional banking, Ahmad et al. (2010) found that Islamic banking has advanced significantly over the past several decades and that its clients seek higher-quality services because they are more informed, aware of their responsibilities, and

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more knowledgeable. If a consumer is pleased, this results in customer retention; if not, it is simple for them to choose another bank. Additionally, they looked at how Islamic banking has made great strides, capturing a sizable portion of the Pakistani industry and growing at a pace of 114% annually. While 13 conventional banks have an Islamic bank window, six Islamic banks operate independently.

According to Akram et al. (2011), Islamic banking is more effective and successful in Muslim nations, particularly Pakistan. Islamic banking has additional difficulties as a result of rivalry with conventional banking in the banking industry, but they are still expanding and outperforming it, which contributes to improvements. Islamic banking must contend with traditional banking if it hopes to rule the financial industry. In Pakistan, Ali et al. (2012) did their research and looked at how traditional banking has worked there ever since Pakistan gained its independence. They also recognized the essential components that draw in and satisfy clients, such as a bank's reputation, its ability to give clients financial advantages, its commitment to client care, the calibre of its services, and its competitiveness. They demonstrate a strong connection between these characteristics and consumer satisfaction in their study. According to Shabbir et al. (2012), providing high-quality services results in customer satisfaction, customer retention, customer loyalty, a decrease in customer complaints, and attempts to enhance service quality. According to Taimoor (2012), a number of variables, including client pleasure, trust, and perception, have an immediate impact on client loyalty. High customer satisfaction and favourable consumer impression of Islamic banks result in greater customer loyalty. Customer loyalty increases when they are certain that Islamic banks are operating in accordance with Islamic norms and principles and without conflict of interest. Trust is another important component since it fosters client loyalty when customers engage with Islamic banks. In order for Islamic banking to maintain both their existing and anticipated levels of client loyalty, they must focus on the dimension of customer loyalty. According to Imtiaz et al. (2013), businesses still like traditional banking since there is no risk of financial loss, interest rates are fixed, profits may be taken from deposits, and profits can be earned in the form of interest on deposits. Businesses don't want to spend more time learning about the products and services that Islamic banks provide, but customers prefer Islamic banking since it is based on moral ideals and respects religious customs and beliefs. Agha and Asghar (2013) found that the management of Pakistan's Islamic banks are well educated and possess a plethora of financial knowledge. The bulk of consumers in Islamic banking deposit money in current accounts with the ability to record earnings and losses, indicating that they are people who are employed and company owners.

Theoretical framework and Hypotheses development

Consumer behaviour and marketing have long explored intention behaviour theories. Most often, the ideas are used to look at behavioural elements that might affect customer decision-making. The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), created in 1977 by Fishbein and Ajzen, is a well-liked approach for researching human purpose and aids in explaining and forecasting behavioural patterns. It is focused on a person's behaviour and desire to commit a specific act. There are two underlying premises in TRA, namely that most human activities are motivated by volitional control and guided by behavioural intents (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). TRA was developed in psychology and has been applied across many academic fields to

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understand human behaviour (Lada, Tanakinjal, & Amin, 2009). TRA has been utilised in the marketing field to examine consumers' intentions to buy halal items (Lada et al., 2009), green products (Ramayah et al., 2010), and luxury goods (Summers, Belleau, & Xu, 2006). TRA has also been utilised to investigate consumer behaviour in the financial services industry (Amin & Chong, 2011). TRA is made up of three concepts: behavioural intention, attitude, and subjective standards. This idea holds that attitudes and subjective standards influence an individual's behavioural intention, which is what causes behaviour to occur. The TPB was incorporated into consumer behaviour as a result of several TRA restrictions, which have drawn criticism. The most significant conceptual framework for analysing human behaviour, TPB, builds on TRA (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977). (Ajzen, 2001). It is based in social psychology and emphasises how beliefs influence behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). TPB is an extension of TRA and takes into account behaviour influenced by non-voluntary external influences (Ajzen, 1985). It consists of four components: attitude, perceived behavioural control, subjective norms, and behavioural intentions. Out of these four components, attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control are indicators of the intention to use Islamic banking in Pakistan. In addition to attitudes and subjective standards, it expands TRA by incorporating perceived behavioural control, which considers volitional aspects when analysing the likelihood of human conduct (Conner & Armitage, 1998).

An attitude is a set of relatively enduring attitudes toward things, people, events, or symbols that have social significance (Vaughan & Hogg, 2005). It may also refer to a psychological tendency that favours or disfavors any entity (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). Suki (2010) claims that attitude describes the degree to which a person views a particular entity as positive or negative. A person's attitude can be used to anticipate their intentions and behaviour (Phau & Teah, 2009). The link between attitudes and behaviours has been established. When given a choice among several possibilities, individuals tend to select the one that receives the most consideration (Arvola, Lähteenmäki, & Tuorila, 1999). Previous research has demonstrated that attitude affects the decision to purchase goods or services (Taib, Ramayah, & Razak, 2008). The body of research on attitude and intention is highly extensive and shows how strongly it affects behavioural intention. Studies have been done on technological integration and general customer behaviour in addition to the setting of Islamic financial services. Ali and Jama (2016) reported on the impact of attitudes on intentions in the context of Islamic insurance; Md Husin and Rehman (2016); Wahyuni and Arifin (2013) discussed the significance of attitudes on intentions in the context of Islamic banking; Gopi and Ramayah (2007) discussed attitudes and intentions with regard to online trade; Ramayah and Suki (2006) discussed the significance of attitudes and intentions in the integration of technology in learning curricula. The evaluation of the existing literature offers suggestions for additional research into this issue in the context of Islamic Banking. For that purpose, it is hypothesized as follows:

H1: Positive attitude has an impact on the intention to adopt Islamic banking.

The word "subjective norms" refers to the influence of social variables, such as societal pressure to display or refrain from displaying a certain behaviour (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). Social forces can sometimes dictate how people feel about certain behaviours (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). Subjective norms are made up of the normative ideas that underlie them and the desire to uphold them. An individual's impression that a certain referent group

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encourages them to behave is what is known as a normative belief, but what motivates someone to comply is the significance of those referent groups. The total of normative views and the weight attached to them makes up subjective norms. According to several research, the influence of subjective standards on behavioural intentions is minimal (Bagozzi, Wong, Abe, & Bergami, 2000). Even if there are contradicting findings in the literature about the link between normative belief systems and behavioural intentions, the topic still needs to be further studied. According to research by Echchabi and Aziz (2012) and Pedersen (2005), subjective standards have a significant impact on how well people estimate their intentions. The subjective standards have also been shown to strongly predict customers' intentions in the financial services industry (Siang & Weng, 2011). Numerous academic fields have conducted studies that have demonstrated how subjective standards have a substantial impact on behavioural intention. For instance, Islamic house finance products (Ali & Jama, 2016; Amin et al., 2016), Islamic insurance (Amin, 2012; Omar & Owusu-Frimpong, 2007), online banking (Amin, 2012; Juwaheer, Pudaruth, & Noyaux, 2012; and Nor, 2013), and home financing are all examples of Islamic financial goods (Razak & Abduh, 2012). Contrary to earlier research, a small number of studies, like those by Md Husin and Rahman (2016) and Saeed, Juell-Skielse, and Uppström (2012), have demonstrated that behavioural intentions are not determined by subjective standards. The contradictory findings of earlier studies highlight the need for more research. Given that the present study is being done in the field of Islamic Banking,

H2: Subjective norms have a positive influence on an individual's intention of adopting Islamic banking

The phrase "any person's perception as to how simple or difficult performance of the behaviour is likely to be" refers to perceived behavioural control (PBC) (Ajzen & Madden, 1986). According to TPB, attitudes, subjective norms, and PBC all work together to shape a person's behaviour. Stronger behavioural intentions to engage in a particular behaviour will result from a more favourable attitude, subjective norms, and PBC. Both motivation and the capacity to carry out a certain act influence behaviour. It is quite likely that a person will not plan to complete a task if they lack the skills or resources necessary to do so (Ajzen, 1989; Schifter & Ajzen, 1985). According to Madden, Ellen, and Ajzen (1992), people who lack the skills or knowledge necessary to carry out a task would have lesser intentions to carry it out while displaying a positive attitude and adhering to subjective standards. Prior research on the connection between PBC and behavioural intention has shown conflicting findings in the literature. A positive correlation between PBC and behavioural intentions has been found in prior research on Islamic banking by Echchabi (2012). A few research, such those by Taylor and Todd (1995) on technology adoption and Beiginia, Besheli, Soluklu, and Ahmadi (2011) on the adoption of mobile banking, have, however, failed to find any conclusive link between PBC and intents. Most research on the adoption of Islamic banking have found a correlation between PCB and intention that is favourable. It is theorised as follows in the context of Pakistan, where the adoption of Islamic banking is still in its early stages:

H3: The perception of behavioural control has a beneficial impact on a person's decision to use Islamic banking.

Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Research Approach The goal of this study is to determine which factor—religion, high profit and low service charges, peer and family influence, service quality, media coverage, staff responsiveness, and bank image—has the greatest influence on consumer behaviour when it comes to choosing an Islamic bank and ultimately on customer satisfaction. **Case Study in Research** The study's sample size was 200, and 14 survey questionnaires were eliminated because of questionable replies, leaving 186 questionnaires that could be used for data analysis. The responders were chosen from among the Multan Division clients of the mentioned Islamic banks. Customers from Dubai Islamic Bank, Al Baraka Bank, Bank Islami Pakistan, Faysal Bank, Dawood Islamic Bank, Meezan Bank, and Burj Bank were the focus of my study. Due to a number of factors, these banks were chosen for the data gathering. As they are account holders at the mentioned banks, I have simple access to the consumer here. Customers with various demographics (such as varying income levels, family and educational backgrounds, etc.) were targeted by me. **Data Gathering Technique** The 30 questions in the questionnaire's items are mostly self-administered, however other studies were referenced to assist ensure accuracy. There were two sections to the questionnaire. The customer's demographic data was provided in section one (gender, age, academic qualification, income, marital status, occupation). Information about customers' interactions with Islamic banks is provided in Section 2 in relation to their religious beliefs, the influence of family and friends, the quality of the services provided, the image of the bank in the media, and the staff's responsiveness, all of which can be used to determine the selection criteria for customer behaviour toward Islamic banks.

Analysis

Profile of Respondents 120 of the 186 responders were men and 66 were women. There were 112 married persons and 74 unmarried people in terms of marital status. A master's degree was held by 104 respondents. 54.8% of respondents reported working for private companies. Furthermore, 85.5% of responders were under the age of 40. In addition, 38.7% of people utilised Islamic banking, compared to 34.9% of those who used conventional banking.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the respondents

<i>Demographic</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender	Male	120	64.5
	Female	66	34.5
Age	21-30 Years	88	47.3
	31-40 Years	71	38.2
	41-50 Years	18	9.7
	Above 50 Years	9	4.8
Occupational Status	Public Sector	50	26.9
	Private Sector	102	54.8
	Self Employed	16	8.6
	Student	14	7.5
	Other	4	2.2

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Marital Status	Single	74	39.8
	Married	112	60.2
Education Level	Diploma	4	2.2
	Professional	20	10.8
	Bachelors	47	25.3
	Masters	104	55.9
Banking	PhD	11	5.9
	Islamic Banking	72	38.7
	Conventional Banking	65	34.9
	Both	39	21.0
	None	10	5.4

SEM findings

Statistical software called Smart PLS was used to analyse this research (Partial least Squares). Both algorithmic and bootstrapping analytic methods have been used to undertake structural equation modelling analysis. Smart PLS-based SEM modelling, according to Hair et al. (2012), is a multivariate modelling approach very similar to regression but significantly more potent in terms of internal consistency reliability of both indicators and latent variables. This is a 2nd generation analytic tool that is increasingly being used by scholars worldwide (Hair et al., 2012).

“The evaluation of the measurement model is the first stage of structural equation modelling. It displays how the variable is related to its items. It can be verified using the HTMT ratio, construct validity (AVE), and discriminant validity calculated by Fornell and Larcker criterion, as well as the assessment of the factor loadings, also known as internal reliability, composite reliability, which calculates internal consistency, and these other methods.” The measurements were made after the smartPLS algorithm had run.

The assessment of the measuring model is summarised in Table 2. All of the constructions' factor loadings are higher than the predetermined benchmark of 0.7; moreover, the loadings for CR and AVE are also higher than 0.5. IR, IC, and CR have been implemented for the constructs used in the model as a result. Furthermore, the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criteria was used to assess the discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2014). The AVE of each concept is compared to the correlations of the other constructs by Fornell and Larcker (1981). Every construct's square root of AVE for the current investigation was higher than its correlations with other constructs. In addition, as indicated in Table 2, HTMT establishes discriminant validity with a cut off value that should be smaller than 0.90. This study's measuring approach provided satisfactory discriminant validity. In light of the measurement model's good reliability and validity, additional structural model analysis was possible.

Table 2. Summary of measurement model assessment

<i>Latent Variable</i>	<i>AVE</i>	<i>DV</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>Indicator (s)</i>	<i>Outer Loadings</i>
<i>Perceived Behavioral control</i>	0.724	0.850	0.867	PBC1	0.812
				PBC2	0.876
<i>Subjective Norms</i>	0.789	0.888	0.734	SN1	0.812

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				SN2	0.789
				SN3	0.765
				SN4	0.811
				SN5	0.854
Attitude	0.761	0.872	0.857	ATDE1	0.744
				ATDE2	0.832
				ATDE3	0.826
				ATDE4	0.769
Adoption	0.719	0.847	0.897	ADPT1	0.752
				ADPT2	0.767
				ADPT3	0.801
				ADPT4	0.812
				ADPT5	0.733

The structural model was analysed after the study of the outer model (measurement model). It contains the prediction accuracy of the model and the connections between the reflective structures. R² and Q² values were computed for that reason. According to Table 3, the model's R² for adoption was 76%, indicating that its explanatory power was adequate. Additionally, a blindfolding approach was used to evaluate the predictive significance. Blindfolding should be used for endogenous variables with reflecting measurements, according to Hair et al. (2014). Values as per Q² > 0 indicates a sufficient level of predictive relevance, and the Q² value for adoption was 0.622, as shown in Table.

Table 1. Path Analysis

Hypothesis	Beta Value	T-Value	F Square	R Square
PBC -> ADPT	0.079	2.432	0.523	
SN -> ADPT	0.352	5.392	0.213	
ATDE -> ADPT	0.528	11.751	0.103	
			Adoption	0.623

Another metric used to assess the structural model is effect-size (f²). The unique result of each external variable on the endogenous variable is examined by f². Cohen (1988) claimed that f² values of 0.523, 0.213, and 0.103, respectively, are classified as small, medium, and big. As a result, as indicated in Table 3, the impact size (f²) of attitude toward the adoption of Islamic banking is significant, whereas that of subjective norms and perceived behavioural control is minor. As a result, we may conclude that the research model had a sufficient predictive significance. To test the hypotheses, the estimates for the path coefficients were obtained. utilising the PLS-SEM method. 5,000 samples were used for the bootstrapping. Table 3 lists the proposed links between the constructs. According to B = 0.528, p 0.01 and t statistics 11.751, H3 represented the relationship between mindset and the implementation of Islamic banking. H2 demonstrated a link between the adoption of Islamic banking and subjective standards, which was confirmed by B = 0.352, p 0.01 and t statistics of 5.392. The relationship between perceived behavioral control and the uptake of Islamic banking was indicated by H1, and it is also supported by B = 0.079, p 0.01 and t statistics 2.432. The data analysis of the current investigation provided evidence in favour of all three hypotheses.

Conclusion

According to the observations and the material reviewed in this study, Islamic banking is one of the most recent and explosive ideas in world economies. Numerous studies indicate that Islamic banking is becoming more popular and inspiring around the world, especially in areas where there are Muslim communities. However, more recent studies refute this claim and acknowledge that people are actually drawn to Islamic banking for a variety of reasons, including the products and services offered by the banks rather than just the religion. This study offers some crucial details on the growth of Islamic banking in Pakistan. The outcome will assist the relevant parties in further advancing the growth of Islamic banking in Pakistan, particularly with regard to customer preference-based selection criteria. However, banks should be aware of the public's limited understanding of the Islamic banking system, particularly while advertising Islamic financial services. Banks should thus adjust their marketing efforts accordingly. As a result, this business needs to hire more knowledgeable professionals or knowledge-based workers to foster increased innovation, particularly when it comes to dealing with Islamic financial products. Due to this, involvement of both public and private colleges in the banking industry may be able to contribute more (for as by creating Islamic financial instruments) to the development of Islamic banking. Islamic banking systems' management and Shariah advisors should make decisions to increase customer satisfaction with the goods and services they offer. The variables influencing and extending Islamic banking are the foundation of this study. This report provides some significant and in-depth information on the growth of Islamic banking in Pakistan while taking all the aspects into consideration. As a consequence, the relevant parties will be able to better, enhance, and build Islamic banking in Pakistan and other nations where people are assisted by Islamic banking with the aid of the formulation of desirable and relevant components from this information. The selection criteria that consumers favour are notably helped by this information. This study also reveals that many individuals are still in the dark about Islamic banking, its principles, and the goods and services it offers. Therefore, banks should be aware of people's limited awareness of the Islamic banking system, as well as their goods and services. The promotion of Islamic financial services including investments, savings, financing, zakat, and the usher system, among others, calls on the Islamic banks to take this crucial step in educating the public and their clients. Consumer knowledge of these services will undoubtedly be advantageous for Islamic banks. As a result, Islamic banks should update and modernise their advertising and other marketing initiatives.

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